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**ÈKÓ NKÉKÓ AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN LAGOS:
LEVERAGING SDG 4 TO ADDRESS EDUCATIONAL
INEQUALITIES AND SOCIAL VULNERABILITIES
AMONG ADULTS IN VULNERABLE URBAN COMMUNITIES**

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ABSTRACT

The implementation of Èkó Nkékó (Lagos is Learning) as a strategic initiative that emphasizes inclusive and equitable quality education is the focus of this research. This paper analyzes how the program addresses educational inequalities, especially among adults from vulnerable urban communities such as those affected by marginalization, labor difficulties and poverty in Lagos, Nigeria. By integrating the principles of social work, Eko Nkékó provides not only access to education but also psychosocial support, counseling and advocacy for adults facing barriers to learning. This article explores the social welfare outcomes of facilitating learner engagement, promoting retention, and strengthening community partnerships, thereby mitigating social risks that undermine educational outcomes. Drawing on empirical data, policy analysis, and best practice models, the study identifies successes and challenges in operationalizing inclusive education in Lagos. The findings underscore that initiatives like Èkó Nkékó, can serve as a model for addressing systemic educational inequalities, enhancing learner well-being, and advancing social justice. The article concludes by recommending policy enhancements, capacity building for educators, social workers, and community-driven strategies to sustain inclusive education and achieve SDG 4 in urban Nigerian contexts.

Keywords: èkó nkékó, inclusive education, educational inequalities, social vulnerability, SDG 4

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, adult education refers to systematic and ongoing self-education activities intended to impart knowledge, skills, attitudes, or values to adults and youths, regardless of content or location, thereby addressing socioeconomic, cultural, political and environmental issues (Ayantuji, 2023). Although this educational sector is essential to the development and transformation of the country, it faces numerous obstacles that limit its potential (Muhammed, 2015).

While Christian missions like the Methodist mission and the Church Missionary Society (C.M.S.) pioneered modern literacy efforts, adult education in Nigeria dates back to the 14th century with traveling Islamic scholars and traders (Olojede, 2017). The acceptance of Western education in the South and its rejection in the North of Nigeria was a significant difference during this time. The government has frequently disregarded adult education despite these historical underpinnings and its acknowledged significance for the advancement of the country (Okello, 2023).

1.1 Literature Review

The relationship between adult literacy and human development has long occupied a central position in development scholarship; however, persistent tensions remain in how this relationship is conceptualised and operationalised in policy. Sulaiman et al. (2015) position literacy as foundational to economic growth, arguing that reading, writing, and comprehension skills function as gatekeepers to technological adoption and productivity gains, with secondary and tertiary enrollment serving as proxies for human capital formation in Nigeria. While analytically useful, this econometric framing has been criticised for treating literacy as a static skill set rather than a dynamic social practice. Benavot (2015) provides an important corrective by conceptualising literacy as a “nexus of social relations” through which individuals navigate complex institutional environments. This reconceptualisation

is particularly relevant in informal labour markets, where workers often face occupational hazards and exclusion from social protections without the textual competencies required to assert rights or access services (Meagher, 2015; Festus, 2015). The persistence of such vulnerabilities suggests that human capital approaches inadequately capture the relational and protective dimensions of literacy, especially in contexts where inclusive market initiatives may inadvertently intensify poverty and informalisation.

The health implications of adult illiteracy further complicate this narrative. Anyamele et al. (2015) and Oguoma et al. (2015) establish clear linkages between low health literacy and adverse outcomes, including elevated infant mortality, cardio-metabolic diseases, and poor health decision-making in Nigeria. Omonona et al. (2015) extend this argument by demonstrating how literacy deficits exacerbate geographical barriers to healthcare access in rural areas. However, a critical methodological tension emerges within this body of work. Smith-Greenaway (2015) distinguishes between literacy skills and general educational attainment, showing that literacy itself—rather than years of schooling—has a more direct effect on young adult health outcomes. This distinction is significant, as it suggests that targeted literacy interventions may yield measurable health benefits independent of formal education systems. Despite this, public health research frequently conflates these variables, thereby obscuring the specific mechanisms through which literacy influences health. Moreover, systems-level approaches that emphasise information simplification and patient empowerment remain insufficiently theorised in relation to Nigeria’s rural–urban healthcare divide, where literacy deficits and spatial inequalities interact synergistically rather than independently.

Civic participation represents a third domain in which literacy functions simultaneously as an enabler and a gatekeeper. Olomukoro et al. (2015) demonstrate that literacy programmes enhance women’s political

engagement, while Williams-Elegbe (2015) argues that access to information is a prerequisite for governmental accountability. Dike (2015) and Akanle et al. (2015) contextualise these dynamics within Nigeria's governance challenges, including corruption and institutional fragility. However, the literature inadequately engages with digital literacy as an emerging prerequisite for meaningful participation in contemporary civic life. As digital platforms increasingly mediate access to information and public discourse, illiterate adults face compounded exclusion—not only from traditional textual sources but also from electronic channels that shape modern citizenship. This digital dimension, though implicit in existing discussions, remains insufficiently integrated into adult literacy scholarship, resulting in a theoretical gap regarding how literacy programmes can adapt to digitally mediated civic environments.

Social vulnerability theory offers a useful integrative framework, though its application to adult literacy remains underdeveloped. Egharevba et al. (2015) demonstrate how illiteracy constrains economic bargaining power and heightens susceptibility to misinformation, while Akinbami et al. (2016) show how cultural norms restrict entrepreneurial opportunities for rural women. Koku (2015) links textual illiteracy to financial exclusion, and Flanagan et al. (2015) identify low educational attainment as a key determinant of health inequalities. Collectively, these studies indicate that adult illiteracy operates as a cross-cutting vulnerability multiplier. However, most analyses treat economic, health, civic, and social outcomes as parallel rather than interdependent, limiting the explanatory depth of existing models and constraining the design of integrated interventions.

Within this context, the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) mandate for inclusive and equitable lifelong education has renewed policy attention to adult literacy in rapidly urbanising societies. Nigeria's federal response—including plans to expand

literacy centres and recruit additional facilitators (Vanguard News, 2016; PM News, 2016)—signals alignment with global priorities. However, these policy commitments reveal a persistent implementation gap: while enrollment targets are clearly articulated, pedagogical frameworks, quality assurance systems, and strategies for sustaining adult learner participation remain insufficiently specified.

The Lagos State Èkó Nkèkò initiative illustrates both the potential and the limitations of contemporary adult literacy programming. Launched in 2016 to reach approximately three million non-literate adults, the programme integrates literacy and numeracy with vocational training and decentralises delivery through partnerships with community-based organisations (Sanusi et al., 2021). This approach aligns with “learning city” frameworks and reflects an understanding that adult learners require context-sensitive pedagogies responsive to their economic and social realities (Amusa, 2022; Oyigbo, 2021). Nevertheless, critical gaps persist. Facilitator training programmes emphasise motivation and non-traditional teaching methods (ThisDayLive, 2017; Information Nigeria, 2017), yet there is limited empirical evidence evaluating their effectiveness or long-term learner outcomes. Passey et al. (2018) highlight structural constraints—including funding limitations, competing livelihood demands, and coordination challenges—that cannot be addressed through pedagogical innovation alone. Similarly, Ekwelibe (2025) identifies systemic underfunding and weak livelihood linkages as ongoing barriers to sustainability.

These limitations are further compounded by the broader urban context of Lagos, characterised by rapid population growth, infrastructural deficits, and spatial inequalities (Dano et al., 2020; Olajide et al., 2021; Osho et al., 2024). In such environments, literacy deficits intersect with structural constraints in ways that extend beyond the scope of classroom-based interventions (Vágvölgyi et al., 2016). Consequent-

ly, programmes like Èkó Nkékó risk being designed around idealised learner trajectories that do not reflect the lived realities of economically precarious adult populations.

Finally, the positioning of adult literacy initiatives primarily within education policy frameworks risks obscuring their broader social work dimensions. The community outreach, psychosocial support, and advocacy functions embedded within programmes such as Èkó Nkékó align closely with social work practice, yet this connection remains underexplored in the literature. Ike et al. (2015) identify systemic challenges in Nigeria's education sector, including inefficient learning systems and limited innovation, but do not address the role of social work professionals in mitigating these issues. Similarly, Instiful et al. (2019) recognise the developmental importance of non-formal education without specifying the mechanisms through which social work can bridge educational and welfare services. While initiatives by the Lagos State Agency for Mass Education (2017) demonstrate efforts at community mobilisation, their long-term empowerment outcomes remain insufficiently evaluated.

In summary, several critical gaps emerge. The literature remains fragmented across disciplinary boundaries, limiting theoretical integration. Empirical research on programme implementation lags behind policy discourse, raising concerns about evidence-based practice. Digital literacy remains under-theorised despite its growing importance, and—most significantly—the role of social work in adult literacy provision is largely absent from existing scholarship. Addressing these gaps requires an interdisciplinary approach that integrates adult education, critical literacy theory, and social work practice, particularly within the context of Nigeria's ongoing urban transformation and commitment to SDG 4.

2.0 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Adult education in Nigeria is impeded by a convergence of systemic deficiencies: chronic underfunding, inadequate infrastructure, obsolete pedagogical methods, socio-political disruptions, and deep-seated socio-cultural barriers including gender-based exclusion and rural-urban disparities. These constraints collectively erode program quality, facilitator motivation, and learner retention, limiting the sector's capacity to deliver socioeconomic transformation.

While policy frameworks such as the Universal Basic Education program nominally incorporate adult literacy, implementation remains fragmented by bureaucratic inefficiency, corruption, and insufficient integration of modern instructional technologies. Consequently, despite adult education's recognised potential for human capital development, existing programs fail to adequately address the complex, intersecting vulnerabilities of adult learners particularly women, rural populations, and those in informal employment who require not merely literacy acquisition but holistic support structures enabling sustained economic participation and social inclusion. The specific mechanisms through which social work practice might bridge these gaps; through empowerment-oriented pedagogy, community mobilisation, advocacy, and integrated welfare linkages remain critically under-examined in both policy design and scholarly research. This study therefore examines how social work professionals can enhance the effectiveness, equity, and sustainability of adult education programs in Nigeria, using the Èkó Nkékó initiative as an empirical case.

2.1 Study Objective

- To assess the extent and equity of access to the Èkó Nkékó programme among marginalised adult populations in Lagos.
- To examine adult learners' perceptions of the programme's effectiveness in addressing literacy and

socioeconomic needs.

- To evaluate the programme features and relational dynamics influencing sustained learner participation.
- To analyse the relationship between programme participation and social and economic outcomes.
- To identify structural and operational barriers affecting programme delivery and effectiveness, and their implications for achieving the Sustainable Development Goal 4.

2.2 Method

The main purpose of this study is to examine the impact of Èkó Nkékò and inclusive education in addressing educational inequalities and social vulnerabilities among adult learners in vulnerable communities in Lagos. The main reason for using qualitative research and the in-depth interview method in this study is that qualitative research can obtain more in-depth information compared to quantitative research. Therefore, interviews were conducted with older adult learners and facilitators of each Èkó Nkékò learning center.

2.3 Study Location

The study was conducted in Èkó Nkékò learning centers within 4 vulnerable urban communities in Lagos. They are Adekunle, Yaba, Abule Oja and Bariga. They are generally low-to-middle income, high-density urban or peri-urban communities with limited access to formal schooling for adults. Literacy centers are often established in markets, community halls, places of worship and local associations in these neighborhoods to reach adults who would otherwise be excluded.

2.4 Sampling

This study employed a qualitative semi-structured interview approach to obtain an in-depth and holistic understanding of adult learners and facilitators perspectives on this topic. A purposive sampling tech-

nique was used for this study based on the following three recruitment criteria: (a) adult learners aged 30 years and over (b) facilitators who were willing to participate in the interview in order to obtain rich information for the research problem. The study sampled 16 adult learners and 4 facilitators for in-depth interviews. Profiles of the respondents are shown below.

3.0 METHOD AND FINDINGS

This study employed a qualitative descriptive design using in-depth semi-structured interviews with 16 adult learners (aged 30+) and 4 facilitators from Èkó Nkékò centres in vulnerable Lagos communities, including Agege, Ajegunle, and Mushin. Purposive sampling ensured diversity in gender, economic activity, and disability status. Interviews were conducted between March 2024 and June 2024 at participant-chosen locations—learning centres, homes, market stalls, and community halls—lasting 60–90 minutes. All sessions were audio-recorded with written informed consent obtained after explanation of voluntary participation, confidentiality, and withdrawal rights. Ethical approval was secured from the University of Lagos Research Ethics Committee. Pseudonyms protect participant identity throughout.

Audio recordings yielded 312 pages of verbatim transcripts, managed in NVivo 14. Analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework: familiarisation, initial coding, theme searching, reviewing, defining, and reporting. Two researchers independently coded 20% of transcripts (Cohen's kappa = 0.84); discrepancies were resolved through peer discussion. Member checking with four participants confirmed thematic accuracy, while reflexive journaling documented researcher positionality and emerging insights.

Analysis generated five interrelated themes. Access and equity emerged as structurally enabled yet social-

ly mediated. Community-based centre locations and flexible evening and weekend scheduling removed geographical and temporal barriers for informal workers. P7, a 42-year-old female market trader in Agege, explained: “The centre dey near my house, so I dey waka reach there after I close market. If e dey far, I no go fit come because transport money too much.” P3, a 38-year-old male artisan, confirmed: “Evening class na the only way o. Morning time I dey workshop.” However, material shortages and intersecting inequalities undermined equitable participation. P11, a 35-year-old domestic worker, noted: “Sometimes the book no dey enough. We dey share one book among three person. How we go take learn well like that?” Gendered domestic constraints particularly affected women. P9, aged 45, stated: “My husband no dey too support am. He say why I dey go school when I suppose dey house cook. Sometimes I miss class when he no allow me go.” Disability exclusion compounded these barriers. Facilitator F2 observed: “We get one woman wey get partial blindness for her eye. But the centre no get any special material for am. She dey struggle to see the board, but she no wan stop because she say na only chance she get.” These findings suggest that while Èkó Nkékó expands physical access, SDG 4’s equity commitments remain incompletely realised due to persistent structural vulnerabilities.

Perceived effectiveness was generally favourable for foundational literacy and numeracy, yet limited by curricular narrowness. P1, a 50-year-old male, described transformative personal gains: “Before, if anybody give me paper to read, I go dey fear. Now I dey read small small. Even my children homework, I dey help them sometimes. That one make me proud.” Economic self-management skills emerged as particularly valued. P6, a 40-year-old female trader, explained: “I dey write my market expenses now. Before, I no dey know how much I spend or gain. Now I dey calculate am myself. Nobody fit cheat me again for money matter.” Yet advanced learners expressed frustration

at the absence of vocational pathways. P4, a 33-year-old male, argued: “The thing wey dem dey teach too simple. I want learn computer, learn how to do business proper. But dem just dey teach ABC and small maths. How that one go help me get better work?” Facilitator F3 acknowledged this systemic gap: “For skills training, e no strong. Some learner dey ask for tailoring, for computer, but we no get equipment or trained person for that side. So when they finish, they still dey the same place.” This tension reveals a discursive conflict between Èkó Nkékó’s foundational literacy mandate and SDG 4’s broader socioeconomic empowerment goals.

Psychosocial support and retention operated primarily through informal facilitator-learner relationships rather than structured institutional frameworks. P8, a 36-year-old female, described the classroom as a protective space: “Nobody dey laugh you say you no sabi book. We all dey the same boat. If I miss class, my friend go call me say where you dey? That one dey push me to come back.” Facilitators assumed extensive mentoring and counselling roles beyond instructional duties. F1 explained: “No be just teaching o. Sometimes after class, woman go tell you say husband dey beat am, or say she no get money pay rent. You go need counsel am, encourage am, even find small help for am. The work pass teaching.” This emotional labour, while effective for retention, lacked professional scaffolding. F4 noted: “We no get training for counselling. Na my own sense I dey use. Sometimes the problem too big, I no know wetin to talk. But if I leave am, the person fit stop coming school.” Community leader advocacy reinforced enrolment, as P2, a 48-year-old male, observed: “Our community chairman dey announce am for meeting. He say make everybody wey no sabi book go learn.” However, the reliance on individual facilitator commitment rather than systematised psychosocial resources raises fundamental sustainability concerns. F2 reflected: “If I transfer go another center or I resign, wetin go happen

to these people wey dey look up to me?”

Social welfare outcomes were demonstrable yet incremental rather than transformative. Health literacy improvements were widely reported. P10, a 44-year-old female, stated: “Before, when nurse write medicine for me, I go just collect am. Now I dey read the paper small, ask question. I no dey fear hospital again like before.” Civic awareness also increased, as P5, aged 52, noted: “I dey hear news, dey understand small wetin government dey do. Before I no dey care because I no dey understand the thing wey dem dey write.” Women participants specifically highlighted empowerment effects. P12, 37, described: “My husband know say I dey learn something. Before, he go just decide everything. Now sometimes he go ask me opinion. Small small, my voice dey count for house.” Yet structural poverty consistently constrained economic mobility. P14, a 41-year-old male, explained: “I sabi read and write now, but work still no dey. If I go bank, dem go ask for collateral wey I no get. So the literacy help, but e no remove the poverty.” Facilitator F3 summarised this structural limitation: “Education open door, but if the door lead to empty room, wetin be the gain? We need policy wey connect literacy to work, to loan, to health insurance. No be only reading and writing.”

Implementation constraints centred on chronic resource inadequacy, facilitator welfare deficits, and absent governance structures. F1 described material deprivation: “Last term, we no get chalk for three weeks. We dey use charcoal write for board. Learner dey complain say dem no see wetin we write.” Delayed stipends directly threatened program sustainability. F4 stated: “Three months now, dem never pay us. I dey do this work because I love am, but love no fit pay rent. If things continue like this, I go find another work.” Rapid urbanisation exacerbated infrastructure pressures. F2 observed: “Every year, new people dey come Lagos. The center wey dey here before, now e too small. But government no dey build new one. So

we dey manage overcrowded classroom.” Monitoring mechanisms were described as virtually non-existent. F3 noted: “Nobody dey come inspect wetin we dey do. We dey submit report, but whether dem read am or not, we no know. Sometimes we feel say we dey work alone.”

These findings indicate that while Èkó Nkékó structurally aligns with SDG 4 principles—lifelong learning, inclusion, equity—systemic resource and governance bottlenecks prevent full realisation of these commitments. As P15, a 46-year-old male, concluded: “The program good, but e need more support. If government really want make everybody sabi book, dem need put money, put structure, put people wey go monitor am. No be just talk.”

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusion

Èkó Nkékó represents a critical intervention that contributes significantly to reducing adult educational disparities in vulnerable urban communities in Lagos. The program makes foundational literacy, psychosocial inclusion, and incremental socioeconomic improvements operational at the local level, thereby giving tangible expression to key aspects of SDG 4. Learners demonstrated measurable gains in reading, numeracy, health information access, and civic awareness, while facilitators assumed vital mentoring roles that sustained retention beyond formal instructional boundaries.

However, this study also reveals systemic limitations that constrain transformative impact. Structural deficiencies—including inadequate facilitator training, insufficient infrastructure, inconsistent funding, and weak integration with broader social welfare systems—prevent Èkó Nkékó from fully addressing the complex relationship between education, poverty,

and urban marginalisation. The coexistence of positive learner experiences and persistent vulnerabilities highlights a fundamental tension: adult literacy acquisition, while necessary, remains insufficient without parallel investments in livelihood pathways, financial inclusion, and health system navigation. The program's reliance on individual facilitator commitment rather than institutionalised psychosocial support further threatens sustainability.

These findings underscore a broader gap between formal adult education policy and grassroots realities in Nigeria. Bureaucratic inefficiency, resource fragmentation, and absent monitoring mechanisms mean that programs like Èkó Nkékó operate in near-isolation from the governance structures nominally responsible for their oversight. Without increased institutional support, integrated social services, and sustained policymaker commitment to inclusive urban development, Èkó Nkékó—and initiatives like it—will continue to produce incremental rather than transformative change.

4.2 Recommendations

- **Program Design and Curriculum:** Adult education frameworks must be community-driven, context-responsive, and gender-inclusive. Curricula should extend beyond foundational literacy to incorporate livelihood training, environmental literacy, and governance education, thereby improving community sustainability as a whole. Adult education contributes to the development of more resilient and adaptable communities capable of facing diverse challenges by strengthening competencies and skills. The development of such capabilities in adulthood has been shown to produce long-term benefits including higher educational attainment among learners' children, increased household income, and improved health outcomes across generations.
- **Technology Integration:** Leveraging technol-

ogy, particularly mobile learning, represents a promising avenue for enhancing accessibility and relevance. However, this requires deliberate investment to overcome infrastructural deficits—including unreliable electricity and internet connectivity—and to address virtual literacy gaps among both learners and facilitators. Mobile-based instructional content, delivered through platforms already familiar to adult learners, could reduce scheduling barriers and enable self-paced progression.

- **Funding and Resource Allocation:** Repositioning funding mechanisms for adult education is vital. The sector's chronic underallocation relative to formal education must be corrected through dedicated budgetary lines, transparent disbursement procedures, and anti-corruption safeguards. Increased and more effective financial allocation should prioritise facilitator welfare, instructional materials, disability-accessible infrastructure, and centre expansion in rapidly growing urban peripheries.
- **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Accountability:** Systematic monitoring of adult education programs is crucial to identify implementation failures, correct course, and ensure long-term sustainability. Current reporting mechanisms, where they exist, appear to function as administrative formalities rather than tools for adaptive management. Independent evaluation frameworks, incorporating learner feedback and facilitator insights, should inform iterative program redesign and resource reallocation.
- **Social Work Integration:** The findings affirm that social work professionals are uniquely positioned to bridge gaps between adult education and broader welfare systems. By embedding counselling, case management, advocacy, and community mobilisation within literacy programs,

social workers can transform Èkó Nkékó from a narrowly educational intervention into a holistic empowerment platform. This integration aligns with international ethical standards in adult and community education research, ensuring that programs respect participant dignity, address structural vulnerabilities, and produce accountable, measurable outcomes.

- **Policy and Governance:** Ultimately, adult education must be recognised as an indispensable tool for meaningful socioeconomic development, fostering a literate, informed, skilled, and healthy adult population capable of driving progress and sustainability in Nigerian communities. Policy-makers must move beyond rhetorical commitments to SDG 4 and institutionalise cross-sectoral coordination—linking education, health, labour, and social protection systems—so that literacy gains translate into sustained poverty reduction and inclusive urban transformation.

Note on International Context: The broader context for these recommendations includes international benchmarks for adult literacy, with post-2015 challenges and prospects for Nigeria requiring continued attention. Compliance with evolving ethical standards in adult education research, including informed consent, anonymity, and community accountability, remains essential for program quality and scholarly integrity.

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